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ABSTRACTBOOK

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Principal component analysis (PCA) of molecular descriptors for improving permeation through the blood-brain barrier of quercetin analogues

Nebojša Pavlović¹, Darko Mitrović², Dragana Zaklan³, Nastasija Milošević⁴, Ana Tomas⁵, Maja Đanić⁶, Momir Mikov⁷

¹ **University of Novi Sad**, Faculty of Medicine, Department of Pharmacy, Hajduk Veljkova 3, Novi Sad, Serbia, nebojsa.pavlovic@mf.uns.ac.rs;

² **University of Novi Sad**, Faculty of Medicine, Department of Pharmacy, Hajduk Veljkova 3, Novi Sad, Serbia, darkoo.mitrovic@gmail.com;

³ **University of Novi Sad**, Faculty of Medicine, Department of Pharmacy, Hajduk Veljkova 3, Novi Sad, Serbia, dragana.zaklan@mf.uns.ac.rs;

⁴ **University of Novi Sad**, Faculty of Medicine, Department of Pharmacy, Hajduk Veljkova 3, Novi Sad, Serbia, nastasijamilosevic@gmail.com;

⁵ **University of Novi Sad**, Faculty of Medicine, Department of Pharmacology and Toxicology, Hajduk Veljkova 3, Novi Sad, Serbia, ana.tomas@mf.uns.ac.rs;

⁶ **University of Novi Sad**, Faculty of Medicine, Department of Pharmacology and Toxicology, Hajduk Veljkova 3, Novi Sad, Serbia, maja.djanic@mf.uns.ac.rs;

⁷ **University of Novi Sad**, Faculty of Medicine, Department of Pharmacology and Toxicology, Hajduk Veljkova 3, Novi Sad, Serbia, momir.mikov@mf.uns.ac.rs

INTRODUCTION

Quercetin is a flavonoid ubiquitously present in vegetables and fruits [1]. Its antioxidant effects are well described and they occur due to its ability to scavenge free radicals, chelate metal ions, inhibit the enzymes responsible for generating free radicals, and modulate expression of genes involved in antioxidant defense. It exerts a wide range of therapeutic effects, such as anti-inflammatory, antimicrobial, chemopreventive, cardioprotective, hypoglycaemic, and neuroprotective [2].

There are numerous studies focused on the neuroprotective effects of quercetin. A recent structure/activity analysis confirmed that quercetin and some of its analogues can significantly affect the activity of inositol phosphate multikinase (IPMK), thus exerting a wide range of pharmacological effects [3]. IPMK is recognized as a multifunctional signaling hub that acts as a kinase and it can produce phosphatidylinositol 3,4,5-trisphosphate (PIP3), which is very important in the patients with Huntington's disease, considering the severely reduced levels of IPMK in the striatum of these patients.

Despite its beneficial effects, the therapeutic use of quercetin is limited due to its poor aqueous solubility and low bioavailability after peroral use. In order to exert its effects in CNS, quercetin has to permeate the brain-blood barrier (BBB), which further limits its therapeutic potential.

The aim of this study was to identify the analogues of quercetin with improved permeation through the BBB and possessing high binding affinities towards IPMK. The molecular descriptors that contribute to better BBB permeation of quercetin analogues will be identified using the PCA strategy, which may be utilized in further drug design of potent IPMK modulators as neuroprotective agents.

METHODS

Molecular docking analysis

3D crystal structure of human IPMK in a complex with quercetin (PDB code: 6M89) was retrieved from the Protein Data Bank and ZINC database was used for screening of ligand structures using the structural similarity search method, which resulted in the identification of 34 quercetin analogues in unionized form. Docking studies were performed using Molegro Virtual Docker (MVD) software.

In silico prediction of CNS distribution

Molecular descriptors relevant to membrane permeability for quercetin and its analogues were predicted using VolSurf+ software (Molecular Discovery, UK). Permeation through BBB was also predicted using the SwissADME web tool, which includes Brain Or Intestinal EstimatedD permeation method (BOILED-Egg evaluation). The interactions of quercetin and its analogues with P-glycoprotein (P-gp) were predicted using PgpRules Server.

Principal Component Analysis (PCA)

The values of size/shape and physicochemical molecular descriptors for each compound in the data set were calculated using VolSurf+ software. PCA was performed in order to substitute the representation of the objects, from the initial representation in the form of the n original intercorrelated variables, into the new principal component (PC) coordinate space.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The ligand-protein interactions were analyzed through the values of MolDock Scores and were expressed as kcal/mol. Binding energies of all tested compounds at the IPMK active site, i.e. the potential energies of the formed ligand-receptor complexes, were in the range from -91.827 kcal/mol for geraldol (Compound 30) to -72.415 kcal/mol for 3,5-dihydroxy-2-(4-phenyl)chromen-4-one (Compound 25). Quercetin had binding energy of -82.233 kcal/mol at the IPMK active site, and out of 34 quercetin analogues tested, 19 compounds exerted higher affinity towards the IPMK active site.

Figure 1. PCA loadings plot (A) and scores plot (B) of molecular descriptors for quercetin analogues

The calculated values of the logarithm of the blood-brain barrier distribution (LgBB) were lower than -0.5 for all quercetin analogues (range: -3.311 to -1.263), indicating the poor brain permeation. Similarly to logP values, 27 analogues had higher values of LgBB than quercetin, with the compound 33 (quercetin 3,4'-dimethyl ether) having the highest LgBB value. 'BOILED-Egg' method also showed

that none of the analyzed compounds can pass through BBB, but the majority of them can be passively absorbed in the intestines. Besides, only 2 compounds, compound 33 (quercetin 3,4'-dimethyl ether) and compound 27 (3-O-methylquercetin), were shown to be the substrates for P-gp, and none of the tested compounds showed P-gp inhibitory activity.

Among 35 compounds, 6 compounds with the highest LgBB values, i.e. with the highest potential to permeate BBB, were marked in the PCA scores plot (Figure 1), along with the quercetin itself (red dot). These quercetin analogues (compounds 13, 17, 22, and 25) are located in the lower left segment of the PCA scores plot (green dots), suggesting that intrinsic solubility and logP have the dominant influence on the ability of quercetin analogues to permeate through the BBB. The exceptions are compounds 27 and 33 that are specific, since they are the only two quercetin analogues that are substrates for P-gp (blue dots).

CONCLUSION

Using several *in silico* methods, it was shown that none of 34 analyzed quercetin analogues have sufficient BBB permeation. However, the application of PCA statistical method in this study proved to be significantly beneficial in the analysis of data regarding the relationship between molecular descriptors and their properties. PCA scores and loadings plots provided information about the influence of a single molecular descriptor on clustering the compounds, regarding their structural characteristics. It was demonstrated that there needs to be a balance between the descriptors related to intrinsic solubility (SOLY) and the ones related to lipophilicity (LOGP n-Oct and LOGP c-Hex) in order to achieve the desired brain distribution. By detecting the molecular descriptors with the strongest contribution to the BBB permeability of quercetin analogues, the synthesis of new compounds with desired properties reflected in favourable values of molecular descriptors is enabled.

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4th European Conference on Pharmaceutics

Advanced technologies enabling new therapies

20 - 21 March 2023, Marseille, France

Dear Colleague,

Following the great success of the last three European Conferences, which were held in Reims, Krakow and Bologna it is our great pleasure to announce the fourth congress of this new series of international meetings, which will be held in Marseille, France, on 20 - 21 March 2023. It will be dedicated to „Advanced technologies enabling new therapies“.

The European Conferences on Pharmaceutics are held every two years (in March/April of the uneven years). They are jointly organized by the A.D.R.I.T.E.L.F. (“Italian Association of Pharmaceutical Technology and Law”), APGI (“International Society of Drug Delivery Sciences and Technology”) and APV (“International Association for Pharmaceutical Technology”).

The aim is to help bridging the gap between fundamental academic research and industrial applications, offering the opportunity to initiate fruitful exchange and cooperation between university and industry. The conference will be a perfect occasion for young as well as for established scientists from academia and industry from all over the world to present their work, network, discuss newest scientific findings and to share their experience with colleagues.

Hot topic session

- Oral drug delivery
- In-silicio simulations
- Advanced therapies
- Personalised medicines

World-wide leading experts in the field will give plenary lectures and invited talks on hot topics. They will give overviews on the current state of the art in the respective domains and outlooks on future perspectives. In addition, latest research findings will be presented in the form of short talks, selected from submitted abstracts. Furthermore, poster presentations will give the opportunity to get an update on the most recent research in pharmaceutics and to personally exchange with the authors.

An industrial exhibition will accompany the conference and allow learning about the latest trends and newest products in the area of pharmaceutical ingredients, developing & processing equipment, analytical technologies, medicinal products, medical devices, contract manufacturing and many other fields.

All coffee and lunch breaks as well as the welcome reception will be included in the registration fees and be held in the industrial exhibition and poster presentation area in order to facilitate discussions between participants, exhibitors and presenters.

We are looking forward to seeing you at the 4th European Conference on Pharmaceutics in Marseille in 2023.

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